

Upgrading the immune response against COVID19: the vitamins and Food Checklist

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The Table aims at summarizing - for the general public - the **food sources** of the micronutrients that are beneficial in upgrading the immune system against the virus discussed in the published article: Importance of Dietary Changes During the Coronavirus Pandemic: How to Upgrade Your Immune Response by Dr Ali Chaari, Dr Ghizlane Bendriss, Dr Dalia Zakaria, Dr Clare McVeigh. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00476/full>

Table 1: Vitamins and Food checklist

Vitamin	Food found	
C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • citrus fruit, such as oranges and orange juice • peppers • strawberries • blackcurrants • broccoli • brussels sprouts • potatoes 	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/vitamins-and-minerals/vitamin-a/
D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • oily fish – such as salmon, sardines, herring and mackerel • red meat • liver • egg yolks • fortified foods – such as some fat spreads and breakfast cereals 	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/vitamins-and-minerals/vitamin-c/
B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thiamin: • peas • some fresh fruits (such as bananas and oranges) • nuts • wholegrain breads • some fortified breakfast cereals • liver • Riboflavin: • milk • eggs • fortified breakfast cereals • mushrooms 	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/vitamins-and-minerals/vitamin-d/

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• plain yoghurt • Niacin:• meat• fish• wheat flour• eggs • Pantothenic acid:• chicken• beef• liver and kidneys• eggs• mushrooms• avocado • B6:• pork• poultry, such as chicken or turkey• some fish• peanuts• soya beans• wheatgerm• oats• bananas• milk• some fortified breakfast cereals • Folic acid/Folate:• broccoli• brussels sprouts• leafy green vegetables, such as cabbage, kale, spring greens and spinach• peas• chickpeas and kidney beans• liver (but avoid this during pregnancy)• breakfast cereals fortified with folic acid • B12:• meat• fish• milk• cheese• eggs• some fortified breakfast cereals	
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E	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • plant oils – such as rapeseed (vegetable oil), sunflower, soya, corn and olive oil • nuts and seeds • wheatgerm – found in cereals and cereal product 	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/vitamins-and-minerals/vitamin-b/
Iron	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • liver • red meat • beans, such as red kidney beans, edamame beans and chickpeas • nuts • dried fruit – such as dried apricots • fortified breakfast cereals • soy bean flour 	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/vitamins-and-minerals/vitamin-e/
Cu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nuts • shellfish • offal 	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/vitamins-and-minerals/iron/
Se	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • brazil nuts • fish • meat • eggs 	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/vitamins-and-minerals/others/
Zn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • meat • shellfish • dairy foods – such as cheese • bread • cereal products – such as wheatgerm 	https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/Selenium-HealthProfessional/#:~:text=Sources%20of%20Selenium-,Food,other%20grains%2C%20and%20dairy%20products.
Polyphenols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Berries • Nuts • Flaxseeds • Herbs and spices • Coffee and tea 	https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/Zinc-HealthProfessional/#:~:text=Oysters%20contain%20more%20zinc%20per,products%20%5B2%2C11%5D.
Protein	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fish • Dairy • Tofu and soy products • Nuts and seeds 	https://www.nature.com/articles/ejcn2010221.pdf?origin=ppub

Amino acids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quinoa • Eggs • Turkey • Cottage cheese • Legumes and beans 	https://www.nutrition.org.uk/nutrition-science/nutrients-food-and-ingredients/protein.html?start=3
Probiotics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yogurt • Kimchi • Kombucha • Sauerkraut 	https://archive.unu.edu/unupress/unupbooks/80129e/80129E03.htm
Vitamin	Food found	https://www.health.harvard.edu/staying-healthy/how-to-get-more-probiotics